

ISic1355

Funerary inscription for Eutychios

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 719

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 20.7 cm

Width 18.5 cm

Depth 2.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-8: 13-20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [π]ίστεως χά
2. [ρι]ν Ἀβραμί [οι]ς ἐ ν ι κόλποις
4. [λ]αχῶν Εὐτύχι [ος] ἐνθάδε κίτε
6. [ζήσ]ας ἔτη λε τε
7. [λευτᾶ] τῆ (πρὸ) ς εἰδ ῶ (ν)
8. []βρίων
9. []

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Here lies Eutybios who, on account of his faith, has received his place in the lap of Abraham.

Having lived 35 years, he died on the 6th day before the Ides of [---]ber.

Translation (it)

Qui giace Eutybios che, per la sua fede, ha ricevuto il suo posto nel grembo di Abramo. Dopo aver
vissuto 35 anni, morì sei giorni prima delle Idi di [---]ber.

Commentary

Eutybios is a fairly common name, but rare in Sicily. The text is Christian, as indicated by the phrase *enthade kite* and the chi-rho symbol at the end, but the initial phrase is strongly Jewish in form. Some have suggested that Eutybios was Jew who converted to Christianity, but it is simpler to see this as a good example of the extensive interaction and influence between the Christian and Jewish communities in ancient Catania.

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Bibliography

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